

Direct electrocaloric characterization of polyvinylidene fluoride-based co- and terpolymers over a wide temperature range

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Abstract

Polyvinylidene fluoride-based polymers have emerged as promising materials for flexible and portable electronics, attracting significant attention as alternatives to electrocaloric ceramics for more energy-efficient cooling. Although many studies report record-high electrocaloric effect values and initial proof-of-concept devices, the lack of comparative temperature-dependent studies and unexplained large discrepancies among various direct electrocaloric characterization methods hinder their full commercial exploitation. In this work, a systematic study of trifluoroethylene-based copolymers and chloro(tri)fluoroethylene-based terpolymers using infrared imaging shows that commercially available polymers can compete with the best electrocaloric ceramics, exhibiting a large electrocaloric effect of ~ 4.5 K at $100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ in several compositions. The proposed direct electrocaloric characterization method captures electrocaloric temperature changes near the adiabatic limit, resulting in lower measurement uncertainty and providing a valuable tool for better understanding discrepancies in reported electrocaloric effects and contributing to standardization. In addition, we show that a simplified Landau indirect approach can reasonably estimate the magnitude of the electrocaloric effect, offering an additional method for evaluating different compositions.

Keywords: PVDF-TrFE, CFE, CTFE, IR camera, electrocaloric

Introduction

Global environmental and energy consumption issues related to climate change are already significantly affecting daily life, and without drastic improvements, forecasts for the near future remain unpromising. These challenges particularly impact cooling technologies and are driving the development of new approaches to heat management.¹⁻⁴ In recent years, the use of caloric effects has emerged as a promising alternative for more energy-efficient and environmentally friendly heating and cooling. Due to its compactness and the simplicity of voltage-controlled thermal changes, the electrocaloric (EC) effect, which refers to the reversible adiabatic temperature change (ΔT_{EC}) or the isothermal entropy change (ΔS_{EC}) of a polar dielectric material when an electric field is applied, can be not only a good alternative to existing cooling technologies but also open possibilities for miniaturization.³⁻⁵

The best electrocaloric cooling performance is currently achieved in ceramic-based regenerators using $PbSc_{1/2}Ta_{1/2}O_3$ multilayer capacitors,⁶⁻⁹ where temperature spans of up to 21 K have been reported.⁹ However, the high energy requirements for processing and limited natural resources make industrialization and widespread commercial use difficult. In contrast, electroactive polymers, particularly the extensively studied polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF)-based polymers, offer a promising alternative. Due to their light weight, flexibility and low processing temperature, these polymers provide an alternative to existing ceramic-based EC technologies and can also be used in the rapidly growing market for portable and flexible electronics. Additionally, PVDF and its derivatives offer a versatile platform for further modification and customization of their properties for targeted applications.^{10,11}

A disadvantage of pure PVDF homopolymer is the stability of the non-ferroelectric alpha crystalline phase and the position of the ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transition (also called the Curie temperature, T_C) above the melting point (i.e., ~ 180 °C), making it unattractive for EC applications. In contrast, copolymerizing VDF with trifluoroethylene (TrFE) favors the ferroelectric beta crystalline phase. In this system, the transition from the ferroelectric to the paraelectric phase occurs below the melting point and can be tailored by varying the amount of TrFE co-monomer added. Since the highest EC effect is achieved near the ferroelectric-paraelectric transition, $P(VDF_{0.55}-TrFE_{0.45})$, or shortly 45TrFE copolymers, exhibit high EC properties, peaking at ~ 70 °C, where ΔT_{EC} values of ~ 12 K (209 V μm^{-1})¹² and ~ 9 K (150 V μm^{-1})¹³ were determined by indirect and direct EC characterization methods, respectively. To further lower the T_C and enable EC applications near room temperature, additional modifications introducing defects into the main polymer chain have been proposed. Adding a third monomer to $P(VDF-TrFE)$, such as bulky chlorofluoroethylene (CFE) or chlorotrifluoroethylene (CTFE) ter-monomers,^{14,15} disrupts the macroscopic ferroelectric domains, resulting in relaxor-like ferroelectric behavior with anomalies in dielectric permittivity and, consequently, a high EC effect near room temperature. $P(VDF_{1-x-y}-TrFE_x-CFE_y)$, or shortly 100xTrFE-100yCFE-based terpolymers, exhibit a high EC effect of several degrees Kelvin at room temperature. However, the reported directly measured ΔT_{EC} values are strongly correlated with the chosen measurement method (for more details, see the Results and Discussion section and Section S12 of the Supporting Information).

In recent years, many new attractive approaches have been used to further improve EC properties, such as irradiation of copolymers,¹⁶⁻¹⁸ formation of composites with ceramic particles¹⁹⁻²¹ or the introduction of double bonds in CFE/CTFE-based terpolymers.²¹⁻²³ However, issues with homogeneous particle distribution, stability of the final polymer material, and the complexity of such systems increase processing costs and limit their large-scale application. To determine which composition performs best in specific temperature ranges, a systematic study of the electrocaloric effect in various commercially available 100xTrFE-based copolymers ($x = 0.3-0.55$) and 100yCFE/CTFE-based terpolymers ($y = 0.07-0.08$) is conducted. Since CFE receives the most attention among the two terpolymers due to its larger dipole moment and the resulting large EC effect at room temperature (Fig. S34 and Table S3, Supporting Information), a direct comparison with CTFE terpolymers is often overlooked in the literature.^{10,24,25} However, it should be noted that due to differences in the reactivity of the starting materials, their price and their availability on a larger scale, only CTFE-based terpolymers are currently suitable for industrial mass production.^{10,25} To address whether CTFE can perform similarly to CFE, two similar compositions, namely the frequently studied 100xTrFE-7CFE and its counterpart 100xTrFE-7CTFE-based terpolymers ($x = 0.25-0.35$), were directly investigated and compared in this work. Supported by structural and electrical characterization, a proportion of up to 7% of a third monomer represents a good compromise between sufficiently pronounced relaxor-like behavior with peak permittivity at room temperature and a sufficient degree of crystallinity (Sections S3 and S7, Supporting Information).

A systematic electrical and electrocaloric characterization of several 100xTrFE-based copolymer and 100yCFE/CTFE-based terpolymer films demonstrates that various compositions perform well. Direct electrocaloric measurements using an infrared camera and numerical modeling reveal a large EC cooling effect of 4.5 K at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ in the ferroelectric 35TrFE and 45TrFE, as well as in the relaxor 7CFE and 7CTFE compositions. The different compositions also exhibit maximum EC effects at different temperatures, ranging from room temperature up to 100 °C, making PVDF-based polymers suitable for various operating temperature ranges. In addition, a simplified Landau phenomenological model that considers low-field permittivity and high-field polarization measurements provides estimates of the magnitude of the EC effect in different PVDF-based compositions. The results are compared with other reported studies, revealing and discussing some discrepancies between different direct measurement methods.

Results and Discussion

Low-field electrical characterization

The investigation of phase transitions, particularly the ferroelectric-to-paraelectric transition (Curie temperature, T_C), at which the highest EC effect is typically achieved,²⁶ was conducted using low-field dielectric permittivity measurements. The temperature and frequency dependence of the real part of the complex relative permittivity (ϵ_r') and the dielectric loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) upon heating of all 100xTrFE-based copolymers ($x = 0.30$ – 0.55) are shown in Fig. 1a and b, respectively. The T_C , identified as the peak in permittivity, decreases with increasing amount of TrFE co-monomer, from ~ 109 °C for 30TrFE to ~ 66 °C for the 55TrFE composition (both measured at 1 kHz). While the shift in T_C to lower temperatures is substantial for TrFE-poor compositions (i.e., ΔT_C of ~ 40 °C from 30TrFE to 45TrFE), it is significantly suppressed as the TrFE content increases further (i.e., ΔT_C of ~ 2 °C from 45TrFE to 55TrFE). T_C of ~ 65 °C appears to represent the lowest achievable limit for TrFE-based copolymers, which is accompanied by a weakening of ferroelectricity in TrFE-rich ($>50\%$) compositions.^{27,28} The stability of T_C at $\sim(70 \pm 5)$ °C on cooling, independent of TrFE content in all copolymers (Fig. S8, Supporting Information), results in significant thermal hysteresis in TrFE-poor ($\leq 35\%$) compositions, which is associated with a first-order ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transition.²⁷⁻³¹ The pronounced asymmetry between heating and cooling (i.e., ΔT_{H-C} of ~ 35 °C in 30TrFE) can be reduced by applying relatively high electric fields, resulting in a ΔT_{H-C} of only ~ 5 °C when $100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ is applied in 30TrFE (see Fig. S9, Supporting Information). In contrast, TrFE-rich compositions ($\geq 45\%$) exhibit no thermal hysteresis and only a slight frequency dependence of peak permittivity (± 3 °C at 0.1–5 kHz). Comparing the peak-permittivity values of the copolymers shows a maximum at the 45TrFE composition, i.e., ~ 55 at 1 kHz (Fig. 1c). This corresponds to the proposed morphotropic phase boundary region found in 45–55TrFE compositions and is related to the competition between defective ferroelectric and relaxor-ferroelectric conformations.^{28,32,33} All TrFE-based copolymers exhibit relatively low dielectric loss tangent, not exceeding 10% across the entire measured temperature range of 5–120 °C at 1 kHz (Fig. 1b). The transition from the first-order ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transition to more relaxor-ferroelectric-like behavior, along with the further decrease in ferroelectricity with increasing TrFE content, was also confirmed by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements (Section S3, Supporting Information) and is consistent with previous reports.^{27-31,34}

The addition of 7% CFE ter-monomer effectively shifts the T_C of the 35TrFE base copolymer composition toward room temperature, resulting in a dielectric peak of ~ 57 at ~ 28 °C and 1 kHz (Fig. 1a and c). This shift is accompanied by a transformation from ferroelectric to relaxor-like behavior, as indicated by a diffuse, frequency-dependent peak in permittivity (Fig. 1a), the absence of thermal hysteresis (Fig. S8, Supporting Information) and no detectable structural phase transitions (Fig. S6, Supporting Information).^{24,35,36} A local maximum in permittivity at ~ 36 °C, observed only on the heating curve of 7CFE, is likely related to compositional heterogeneity in the sample. Increasing the CFE content to 8% further reduces crystallinity and, consequently, the dielectric response (Sections S3 and S7, Supporting Information), making the 7CFE composition preferable for further electrocaloric

characterization.^{37,38} On the other hand, adding 7% CTFE ter-monomer is less effective at shifting the T_C of the copolymers toward room temperature and results in ~9% lower peak-permittivity value of ~52 at ~50 °C and 1 kHz (Fig. 1a and c). This behavior is attributed to the dipole moment of the CTFE ter-monomer being nearly three times lower than that of CFE, making CTFE less polar and less responsive to an external electric field.^{10,25} 7CTFE also exhibits relaxor-like behavior, characterized by a diffuse, frequency-dependent peak in permittivity (Fig. 1a) and the absence of thermal hysteresis (Fig. S8, Supporting Information).^{14,15,34} However, DSC analysis revealed the coexistence of several presumably ferroelectric and relaxor phases, indicating a more heterogeneous nature of the sample (Fig. S6, Supporting Information). A direct comparison of the 7CFE and 7CTFE compositions shows that CFE converts the copolymer into relaxors more effectively and brings the peak permittivity closer to room temperature, as supported by thermal analysis (Section S3, Supporting Information) and consistent with the literature.^{10,24,35,37,38}

Low-field dielectric permittivity measurements, particularly the slope of the reciprocal dielectric constant above T_C , can be used to calculate the β coefficient and thus indirectly estimate the magnitude of the EC effect in ferroelectric materials according to the Landau phenomenological approach (Eqs. 1 and 2, Materials and Methods).³⁹⁻⁴¹ To avoid the influence of thermal hysteresis and the related stability of T_C during cooling, the slope of dielectric permittivity upon heating (Fig. 1a) was used for calculations. The diffuse and broad permittivity peak of 7CFE results in the lowest β coefficient of $1.87 \cdot 10^7 \text{ Vm K}^{-1} \text{A}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$, while the highest β value of $4.95 \cdot 10^7 \text{ Vm K}^{-1} \text{A}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ is obtained for the 55TrFE copolymer (Fig. 1d).

Figure 1. Temperature dependence of (a) ϵ_r' at different frequencies and (b) $\tan \delta$ at 1 kHz during heating of 100xTrFE ($x = 0.30-0.55$) copolymer, 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymer films. (c) Room-temperature and peak values of ϵ_r' and (d) reciprocal ϵ_r' at 1 kHz during heating above T_c and the resulting β coefficients.

High-field electrical characterization

The transformation of a ferroelectric from a first-order phase transition to more pronounced relaxor-like behavior, along with the further decrease in ferroelectricity as TrFE content increases in P(VDF-TrFE) copolymers, is also evident from the room-temperature polarization–electric field (P – E) hysteresis loops. Examples of bipolar P – E hysteresis loops measured at 25 °C and $110 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ are shown in Fig. 2a, while P – E and corresponding current density–electric field (j – E) loops at different field amplitudes are shown in Section S5 (Supporting Information). At room temperature, the maximum polarization (P_{max}), remanent polarization (P_r) and electric coercive field (E_c) decrease with increasing TrFE content in the copolymers, which is directly related to the lower dipole moment of TrFE compared to the VDF co-monomer (Fig. 2c).^{25,28} It should be noted that all copolymers are in the ferroelectric phase at room temperature, although their different proximity to the ferroelectric–paraelectric phase transitions may have a slight influence.

For both 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymers, pronounced relaxor behavior is also evident in the high-field P - E and j - E hysteresis loops, which show slimmer, tilted loops and double switching current peaks at room temperature (Figs. 2b and S12, Supporting Information). Interestingly, nearly identical P_r and E_c values were obtained for both compositions, while the P_{\max} value is about 25% higher in the 7CFE composition, i.e., $\sim 6.4 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ compared to $\sim 5.1 \mu\text{C cm}^{-2}$ in 7CTFE (Fig. 2b and c). This difference is related to the threefold difference in polarity between CFE and CTFE ter-monomers,^{10,25} which is already evident in the low-field permittivity measurements. In addition, the different properties of the two ter-monomers also affect the shape of the P - E hysteresis loops, with 7CFE showing more double-like or pinched hysteresis loops, while 7CTFE shows a single, more ferroelectric-like hysteresis loop (Figs. 2b and S12, Supporting Information). Such double-like hysteresis loops have been observed previously and are likely related to the electric field-induced ferroelectric switching, which is strongly influenced by the physical pinning of the polymer chains in these terpolymers, with the stronger pinning effect of CTFE causing it to be less responsive to an external electric field.^{10,14,25,38,42}

Like copolymers, the varying proximity to relaxor-ferroelectric transitions or anomalies in terpolymers could influence the results. Therefore, temperature-dependent polarization measurements are required for further confirmation. $P(T,E)$ data for PVDF-based polymers, which are commonly used to estimate the magnitude of the EC effect in ferroelectrics using the well-known indirect Maxwell method or the phenomenological Landau approach,^{39-41,43} are rarely found in the literature, especially across wide temperature ranges that cover the (relaxor)ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transitions discussed above. To mimic the reversible conditions during the EC cycle, unipolar P - E loops of copolymers and terpolymers were collected, from which temperature- and field-dependent P_{\max} values were obtained (Section S6, Supporting Information). Comparison of the room temperature P_{\max} values of TrFE-based copolymers obtained from unipolar loops shows the opposite trend compared to bipolar loops (Fig. 2c); namely, in unipolar loops, P_{\max} increases with increasing TrFE content, consistent with pronounced relaxor character (Fig. 2d). Comparison of the $P(T)$ data obtained at low applied electric fields ($<50 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$) agrees well with the low-field permittivity measurements (Fig. 1a), showing peak values for 35TrFE, 45TrFE and 50TrFE copolymers at $\sim 95^\circ\text{C}$, $\sim 65^\circ\text{C}$ and $\sim 65^\circ\text{C}$, respectively (Fig. S14, Supporting Information). Similar to ceramic ferroelectrics, the peak polarization becomes broader and less pronounced at higher applied electric fields (e.g., $100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ in Fig. 2d), resulting from stabilization of the ferroelectric phase by the external field. Interestingly, however, the field-induced shift of the peak toward higher temperatures appears less pronounced than in ceramics, and the peak may even shift slightly toward lower temperatures. A mechanism for this different behavior in polymers is unknown and has not yet been explained in literature. Despite the use of a higher frequency (i.e., 100 Hz), increased conductivity could lead to a slight overestimation of the P_{\max} values at higher temperatures ($>80^\circ\text{C}$). Due to the excessively high T_C of 30TrFE ($\sim 110^\circ\text{C}$) and the weaker ferroelectric response of 55TrFE, both compositions were excluded from further studies on temperature-dependent polarization and EC characterization.

On the other hand, no obvious peak at $P_{\max}(T)$ was observed for both terpolymers (Figs. 2d and S16, Supporting Information), consistent with the relaxor-like nature of the samples. However, a broad peak anomaly observed at low fields in 7CTFE at ~ 50 °C may reflect the more pronounced ferroelectric character previously suggested by DSC (Fig. S6, Supporting Information) and dielectric permittivity measurements (Fig. 1a). 7CTFE shows ~ 20 – 25% lower polarization values compared to the 7CFE composition over the entire measured temperature range, confirming the results of the bipolar P – E loops at room temperature (Fig. 2b). Comparison of the 7CFE and 8CFE compositions also shows a similar trend, i.e., $\sim 15\%$ lower $P_{\max}(T)$ values over the entire measured temperature range (Fig. S19, Supporting Information), confirming the detrimental effects of reduced crystallinity in 8CFE on the ferroelectric properties of the material. In summary, the $P(T)$ measurements confirm the results of the low-field electrical characterization and indicate that the highest EC effect is expected near the (relaxor) ferroelectric-paraelectric phase transitions. A sequence of transitions covering a wide temperature range from room temperature (7CFE) to ~ 100 °C (35TrFE) represents several promising copolymer and terpolymer compositions for further direct EC characterization.

Figure 2. Bipolar P – E hysteresis loops of (a) 100xTrFE copolymers ($x=0.30$ – 0.55) and (b) 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymers at 25 °C, 1 Hz and $\sim 110 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, with (c) corresponding P_{\max} , P_r and E_c values. (d) Temperature dependence of P_{\max} determined from unipolar P – E loops measured at 100 Hz and $\sim 110 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$.

Direct electrocaloric characterization with infrared imaging

Based on the results of the electrical characterization, three copolymer (i.e., 35TrFE, 45TrFE and 50TrFE) and two terpolymer (i.e., 7CFE and 7CTFE) compositions were selected for further direct EC characterizations. For accurate and reliable temperature measurements with an IR camera, the emissivity of the sample must be larger than 0.6, meaning the sample surface emits at least 60% of the thermal radiation compared to a blackbody at the same temperature.⁴⁴ Since many materials, especially metal electrodes with emissivity typically less than 0.2, do not meet this criterion, the surface emissivity must be increased by additional coating and accurately calibrated. Insufficient or inaccurate emissivity results in incorrect absolute temperature measurements and affects the magnitude of the measured ΔT , leading to large measurement errors and ultimately significant overestimation of the EC effect, as demonstrated in the example of the 7CFE terpolymer (Fig. S27, Supporting Information).

In this work, the EC-induced ΔT of the films was obtained from printed black ink layers, with emissivity calibrated using the known ambient temperature measured on the thick black ink (Fig. S21, Supporting Information). Typical measured EC cycles, consisting of adiabatic polarization (EC heating) and adiabatic depolarization (EC cooling) for different compositions and temperatures at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, are shown in Fig. 3a. Temperature- and field-dependent EC measurements were performed on several printed ink-coated surfaces and are presented as the mean and standard deviation of 3–4 consecutive EC cooling peaks, as shown in the examples in Fig. S22, Supporting Information. The temperature-dependent EC cooling effect of five studied copolymer and terpolymer compositions at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ is shown in Fig. 3b, while measurements for both EC heating and EC cooling at different electric fields can be seen in Figs. S23 and S24, Supporting Information. EC effect measurements at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ reveal a sequence of separated and well-defined peaks ranging from near room temperature to $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. It appears that CFE- and CTFE-based terpolymers do not behave like classical ceramic relaxors, where, in contrast to ferroelectrics, a temperature-independent EC response is typically achieved over a relatively wide temperature range.^{45,46} Interestingly, the peak values for 7CFE, 7CTFE, 45TrFE and 35TrFE at $\sim 39 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\sim 54 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\sim 72 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $\sim 93 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively, show a similar EC-induced ΔT of $\sim 4 \text{ K}$ regardless of the type of material, i.e., ferroelectric or relaxor-like behavior (Fig. 3b), making PVDF-based polymers an attractive system for targeted tailoring of the EC response. On the other hand, 50TrFE does not follow the same trend due to a weakening of ferroelectric character observed in TrFE-rich compositions, resulting in a ΔT of $\sim 3 \text{ K}$ at $\sim 74 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. 3b).

In contrast to the results at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, the dependence of peak EC values on field amplitude varies among the different compositions. For example, terpolymers show the largest increase in the EC effect at low electric fields (see ΔT increments at $\sim 50 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, shown in light blue in Fig. 3c), while the largest increase in ΔT for copolymers typically occurs above $\sim 75 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (shown as light green increments in Fig. 3c). This reflects differences in E_c , as relaxor compositions respond better at low applied electric fields, whereas ferroelectric copolymers require higher fields to induce a large change in P_{max} (Fig. 2d). For copolymers, the maximum EC effect decreases with increasing TrFE content reaching 4.6 K at 50TrFE, 5.3 K at 45TrFE and 8.1 K at 35TrFE (all at $\sim 150 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$). A comparison of the EC effect at $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

shows that 7CFE is by far the best composition for near room-temperature applications, reaching ~ 3.2 K at ~ 100 V μm^{-1} (Fig. 3d). The EC effect at 30 °C is strongly influenced by the proximity of the (relaxor) ferroelectric–paraelectric phase transition, resulting in a $\sim 33\%$ lower ΔT in 7CTFE and a $\sim 69\%$ lower ΔT in 45TrFE compared to the 7CFE composition. EC measurements on several different films for each copolymer and terpolymer composition at 30 °C and at temperatures corresponding to the peak ΔT_{EC} values show good repeatability of the characterization method, with comparable results obtained despite slight differences in the thicknesses of the polymer films and black ink layers (Figs. S25 and S26, Supporting Information). Additionally, the results reveal a general trend that copolymers can withstand higher electric field amplitudes than terpolymers.

Figure 3. (a) EC cycles measured at different temperatures and ~ 100 V μm^{-1} , and (b) temperature dependence of EC-induced ΔT for the cooling of 100xTrFE copolymers ($x = 0.35\text{--}0.50$) and 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymers at ~ 100 V μm^{-1} . Electric field dependent ΔT cooling of copolymers and terpolymers at (c) temperatures at which maximum values were obtained and (d) at 30 °C.

Despite the relatively low thermal conductivity of polymers (~ 0.2 W $\text{m}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$) and the absence of a substrate, some of the EC-induced heat could be dissipated in the EC inactive parts of the sample stack (mainly the printed black ink layers) before it was detected by the IR

camera.⁴⁷ The influence of the different thickness ratio of polymer film and black ink layer and thus the different ratio of EC-active and non-active thermal mass (Fig. S21c, Supporting Information) can be directly recognized by the shape of the EC-induced peaks and the associated slope of thermal relaxation in EC cycles (Figs. 3a and S22, Supporting Information). Therefore, adiabatic or intrinsic ΔT_{EC} are required for a better comparison of EC measurement results. Like our previous work on ceramic films,⁴⁷ a heat dissipation study was performed using numerical simulations, in which a correction factor (k), defined as the ratio between the intrinsic EC effect (ΔT_{EC}) and the measured EC-induced ΔT , was determined (see Section S10, Supporting Information, for more details).

Numerical modeling of different samples revealed that k is in the range of ~ 1.1 – 1.2 , indicating that ~ 10 – 20% of the EC-induced heat is dissipated in the non-active parts before being detected by the IR camera (Fig. S30, Supporting Information). The results are in good agreement with the differences in thickness ratio between the polymer and black ink layers (Fig. S29, Supporting Information). As a faster and simpler alternative to numerical modeling, a straightforward calculation of the EC-induced heat and its distribution in the polymer and black ink layers can also provide a good approximation of a correction factor ($\pm 3\%$ compared to modeling, see Section S10 of the Supporting Information for more details). Newly corrected adiabatic EC cooling values for the five investigated copolymer and terpolymer compositions at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (Fig. 4a) show a sequence of nearly identical peak values of $\sim 4.5 \text{ K}$, independent of composition, i.e., 35TrFE and 45TrFE copolymers or 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymers. Since all four compositions exhibit a relatively high EC effect at a moderate electric field, selecting the best candidate depends on the operating temperature range of the intended applications. Both terpolymer compositions perform best at or just above room temperature, while the copolymers are better suited for higher temperatures (i.e., 60 – $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Additionally, such a sequence of peaks with high EC effect enables the possibility of stacking or cascading different compositions to increase the temperature span of the EC device and improve its energy efficiency, as already demonstrated for magnetocaloric counterparts.⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰

The comparison of the results with the literature, which focuses almost exclusively on 45TrFE copolymers and CFE terpolymers, is challenging because results from various research groups using different direct methods vary significantly (see Section S12, Supporting Information). Aside from a recent room-temperature characterization of irradiated films,¹⁸ the EC effect of 45TrFE copolymers has not yet been studied with an IR camera. However, comparing the peak ΔT_{EC} values near the T_{C} reveals some discrepancies compared to other direct methods. Direct EC measurements using a thermistor in a calorimeter show significantly larger values than the results obtained in this work, with differences exceeding a factor of 2 at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ (see Fig. S33 and Table S2, Supporting Information for more details). Conversely, more studies on CFE terpolymers have been performed using different direct EC methods. A comparison of the ΔT_{EC} values of different CFE compositions obtained near room temperature (25 – $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) is shown in Fig. S34 and Table S3 in the Supporting Information (note that only unmodified CFE compositions were used for comparison). The EC effect of 7CFE agrees well with other reported values also determined with an IR camera. Moreover, the results also fit well with another direct characterization method, namely modified DSC (see green and blue symbols in Fig. S34, Supporting Information). On the other hand, a direct method using a heat

flux sensor (black symbols in Fig. S34, Supporting Information) generally leads to much higher values, on average by a factor of 2 or even higher than the EC effect values determined with the IR camera and the DSC method. In addition, the heat flux method shows a larger scatter of results from the different reported studies. All relevant literature data used for the comparison as well as more detailed analysis of the reported values can be found in Section S12, Supporting Information. Given the significant differences between the heat flux method for CFE terpolymers and the thermistor method for 45TrFE copolymers, compared to IR imaging and calorimetry, it is difficult to determine which method provides more accurate results. With increasing interest in EC polymers and a growing number of related publications, it is important to address this issue to gain a clear understanding and to encourage more critical comparisons of the different direct EC characterization methods. Characterizing the same sample by different research groups using various measurement methods may be the only way to determine whether certain methods tend to underestimate or overestimate the values of the EC effect in polymers. This question can also be addressed by increasing the active mass of the material, for example, by fabricating multilayer capacitors that minimize rapid heat dissipation during EC characterization, resulting in minimal or negligible correction factors and lower measurement uncertainties. Additionally, developing new EC heat pump prototypes, where overall device performance can be linked to the intrinsic EC effect of the components, as has already been demonstrated with ceramic multilayer capacitors, is another viable solution.^{8,9}

Indirect estimation of electrocaloric effect

As direct EC methods typically require more time and specialized measuring equipment, indirect measurements provide a useful tool for quickly screening the properties of different materials and estimating the order of magnitude of the expected EC effect. Additionally, comparing trends obtained from indirect methods can help evaluate reported direct measurements and critically compare their results, as mentioned before. However, results obtained indirectly should be considered rough estimates due to necessary assumptions and should always be compared with direct measurements. The indirect Landau phenomenological approach allows fast and simple prediction of ΔT_{EC} by using easily accessible low-field permittivity and high-field polarization data without solving any nontrivial integrals (Eqs. 1 and 2, Materials and Methods).³⁹⁻⁴¹ β -coefficients and P_{max}^2 values obtained at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ for three copolymer and two terpolymer compositions are shown in Fig. 4b. For the copolymers, the β -coefficient increases as TrFE content increases, while P_{max}^2 decreases. In contrast, the 7CFE composition has the lowest β value but one of the highest P_{max}^2 values. Since the EC entropy change is related to the product of these two quantities (Eq. 1, Materials and Methods), there is a trade-off. However, according to the Landau model, the best way to achieve a high EC effect is to increase β while maintaining a large P . The indirectly obtained ΔT_{EC} was then calculated from ΔS_{EC} , taking into account the c_p of the material (Section S9, Supporting Information).

The calculated ΔT_{EC} peak values for all studied compositions at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, along with their comparison to the directly obtained peak EC effect values, are shown in Fig. 4c. Temperature- and field-dependent data are provided in Figs. S31 and S32 in the Supporting Information. Comparing the peak ΔT_{EC} values for copolymers shows that the simplified indirect

Landau model used here yields larger ΔT_{EC} values (i.e., ~20-30% at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$) compared to the directly measured results in this work. This is consistent with the literature, where, for the 45TrFE composition, indirect methods often report larger values than those obtained with the IR camera (Fig. S33, Supporting Information).^{12,51} Previous reports suggest that this difference may result from the semi-crystalline nature of the polymers and/or from neglecting higher-order coefficients and their temperature dependence in the model.^{12,39-41} On the other hand, for both terpolymer compositions, a slight underestimation (i.e., up to ~20% at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$) of the indirectly determined EC peak values compared to the directly measured values was observed (Fig. 4c). These results are consistent with previous work and may be attributed to the ergodic nature of the relaxor materials or the non-negligible secondary pyroelectric effect related to induced dimensional changes of the terpolymers.^{12,40,41,52} Note that this method is valid only at the phase transition, therefore, this comparison was made solely for the peak values (not necessarily obtained at the same temperature), while somewhat larger discrepancies can be observed when comparing the temperature-dependent values (Fig. S32, Supporting Information), especially at higher electric fields, where the differences are more pronounced. It is known that the Landau phenomenological model does not account for the saturation of polarization at larger fields and tends to broaden the width of the calculated peaks due to the assumption of temperature-independent coefficients, as observed in the case of BaTiO₃ ceramics.^{39,41} In summary, despite the use of the highly simplified Landau model, the method works quite well (within an error of $\pm 30\%$) and can therefore be used as a quick tool to estimate the order of magnitude of the EC effect in different polymer materials. Interestingly, many discrepancies among different direct EC measurement methods cannot be explained by their dielectric permittivity and polarization data.

Figure 4. (a) Temperature dependence of ΔT_{EC} for the cooling effect determined with the IR camera and numerical modeling, (b) relationship between β -coefficient and P_{max}^2 at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ and (c) directly vs. indirectly obtained ΔT_{EC} for the cooling effect at $\sim 100 \text{ V } \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ of 100xTrFE copolymers ($x = 0.35\text{--}0.50$) and 7CFE and 7CTFE terpolymers.

Conclusions

A systematic electrocaloric study of commercially available TrFE-based copolymers and CFE/CTFE-based terpolymers was performed using direct IR imaging and numerical modeling. The results show that 7CFE, 7CTFE, 45TrFE and 35TrFE exhibit distinct maximum EC effects, each peaking at different temperatures between room temperature and 100 °C (i.e., ~39 °C, ~54 °C, ~72 °C and ~93 °C, respectively). At their optimal temperatures, all four compositions perform equally well, exhibiting a large EC effect of ~4.5 K at a moderate electric field of 100 V μm^{-1} , demonstrating that commercial polymers can compete with the current best lead-based EC ceramics.^{6,53-55} Therefore, selecting the best candidate depends on the operating temperature range of the intended application or, alternatively, allows for stacking or cascading different materials to increase the operating temperature window of EC devices.⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸

The comparison of the obtained EC effect with values reported in the literature reveals a large discrepancy among the various direct characterization methods developed in recent decades. Given the increasing interest in EC polymers and the growing number of publications and proposed devices, a critical evaluation is necessary. Since the intrinsic EC effect is crucial for the design, development and potential mass production of future polymer-based heat pumps, an accurate assessment is timely. The fast thermometry using a commercial IR camera employed in this work enables capturing EC-induced ΔT close to adiabatic conditions, minimizing the difference between measured and intrinsic ΔT , and thus reducing measurement uncertainty by minimizing the need for large conversion or correction factors. We believe the versatility of IR imaging for characterizing temperature changes, from thin single-layer films to macroscopic devices, could establish the method as a standard in future direct characterization of the EC effect and as a key tool to better understand the origin of large discrepancies in reported results. Indirect EC measurement methods, often used to estimate the order of magnitude of the EC effect, can also help quickly evaluate results obtained with direct methods. In this work, we have shown that even a highly simplified Landau phenomenological model performs reasonably well and can therefore be used as a convenient tool for screening different PVDF-based polymer materials by addressing readily accessible low-field permittivity and high-field polarization data.

Despite the high EC effect shown in single-layer films of commercial polymers in this work, a larger thermal mass is needed to further advance the use of polymers in practical applications. As demonstrated with EC ceramics, multilayer capacitors can increase the active mass of the material and improve the mechanical stability of the active elements without increasing the voltage required to trigger the EC effect. Therefore, fabricating reliable polymer multilayer capacitors is the next necessary step toward functional EC components.

Materials and Methods

Polymer films fabrication

P(VDF_{1-x}-TrFE_x) copolymer powders, denoted here as 100xTrFE ($x = 0.30, 0.35, 0.45, 0.50$ and 0.55), P(VDF_{1-x-y}-TrFE_x-CFE_y) terpolymer powders, denoted as 100xTrFE-100yCFE (i.e., 32TrFE-8CFE and 31TrFE-7CFE) or shortly 100yCFE ($y = 0.08$ and 0.07) and P(VDF_{1-x-y}-TrFE_x-CTFE_y) terpolymer powder, denoted as 100xTrFE-100yCTFE (i.e., 28TrFE-7CTFE) or shortly 100yCTFE ($y = 0.07$) were obtained from Arkema-Piezotech, France. The exact average compositions and batch numbers are listed in the Supporting Information (Fig. S1).

To prepare free-standing polymer films, PVDF-based powders were dissolved in 2-butanone ($\geq 99.0\%$, Sigma-Aldrich) at room temperature to obtain a 10 wt.% solution, which was applied to a glass substrate using a blade coater (TQC Sheen, The Netherlands). The uniformly deposited films were dried at room temperature and crystallized by annealing at ~ 10 – 20 °C below the melting point of the polymers. After crystallization, the polymer films were removed from the glass substrate by immersion in deionized water, followed by drying at 80 °C. For electrical characterization, ~ 100 nm thick Au electrodes were deposited through a shadow mask using a planar magnetron sputtering system (Bal-Tec, MED 020). Round electrodes with a diameter of 4–6 mm were used for all electrical measurements. For the electrical contacts, Cu wires (diameter 0.1 mm, Block, Germany) were bonded with silver epoxy (RS PRO, Germany). Further details on sample preparation and processing conditions selection are provided in the Supporting Information (Section S1 and Fig. S2).

The film thickness was verified from cross-sections using optical microscopy. Electroded samples were precisely cut with a cryo-ultramicrotome (EM UC6, Leica Microsystems), yielding a typical thickness range of 8 μm to 12 μm for all studied samples (Fig. S3, Supporting Information). The density of non-electroded polymer films was determined using a He pycnometer (Micromeritics, AccuPyc II 1340) at room temperature, resulting in a density of 1.88 g cm⁻³ for all copolymers and 1.78 g cm⁻³ for all terpolymers.

Thermal changes associated with structural phase transitions of the polymers were investigated using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC 3+, Mettler Toledo, Switzerland). Measurements were conducted on as-received PVDF-based powders. To eliminate any possible imprint from powder processing, two heating and cooling cycles were performed for each composition in the temperature range of 0–180 °C at heating and cooling rates of 5 K min⁻¹. Further details are provided in the Supporting Information (Section S3).

Electrical characterization

The relative dielectric permittivity (ϵ_r) and dielectric loss tangent ($\tan\delta$) as functions of temperature were analyzed using an Aixacct TF analyzer 2000E (aixACCT Systems, Germany). Measurements were performed on unpoled samples during heating and cooling runs between 5 °C and 120 °C (temperature stabilization at every 1 °C) in the frequency range of 0.1–5 kHz using an AC voltage signal of 0.15 V.

The same Aixacct TF analyzer 2000E system was used to measure unipolar and bipolar AC current density–electric field (j – E) hysteresis loops as a function of temperature, from which polarization–electric field (P – E) hysteresis loops were simultaneously determined by numerical integration of the current signal using the Aixacct software. Measurements were performed over a temperature range of 10–90 °C in 5 °C increments, using a triangular waveform at 1 Hz and 100 Hz and electric fields up to 140 V μm^{-1} . The temperature- and field-dependent maximum (P_{max}) and remanent (P_r) polarization values were extracted from each individual P – E loop.

Direct electrocaloric measurements

The direct measurement of the EC effect was performed using a commercial infrared (IR) camera (FLIR X6580sc). Measurements followed the same setup and protocol described in our previous work.⁴⁷ To ensure sufficiently high emissivity for accurate sample temperature monitoring (i.e., >0.6 over the entire temperature range), two black ink coatings of different thicknesses were applied to the samples before measurement (see example in Fig. S21a, Supporting Information). First, thick black ink dots (black matte spray, Colorjelt RAL 9005, Jelt) were manually applied to the EC-inactive (non-electroded) part of the sample to bring the emissivity close to 1, allowing the actual base temperature of the sample to be obtained at any time. Second, to minimize the amount of EC-inactive material on the EC-active part of the sample, only small squares of 3–5 μm thick black ink layers were printed on the top Au electrode using a commercial office printer and cartridges (Lexmark XC9635). The measured EC temperature change (ΔT) of a sample was determined solely from the printed black ink layers, with emissivity calculated based on the base temperature measured on the thick black ink dots. An example of an IR thermogram and the temperature dependence of the calibrated emissivity for all measured compositions are shown in Fig. S21b and c, respectively, in the Supporting Information. Balancing sufficiently high emissivity for accurate temperature monitoring (i.e., always greater than 0.6) with the thinnest possible printed black ink layer, combined with a high IR camera frame rate of 1.35 kHz, enabled measurement of ΔT as close to adiabatic conditions as possible. To trigger the EC cycle, a unipolar step-like electrical signal was applied using a function generator (Keithley 3390, Tektronix, USA) and a high-voltage amplifier (Trek 2220), while the sample temperature was controlled using a Linkam temperature stage (THM S600 with LNP95, UK).

To determine the adiabatic EC temperature change (ΔT_{EC}) of polymer films, finite element modeling was performed using the heat transfer module in COMSOL Multiphysics (version 5.6). A numerical 2D model was created based on the exact structures and dimensions of the experimentally examined sample stacks. The thicknesses and physical properties of all layers used to create the numerical model are summarized in Fig. S29 in the Supporting Information. A user-controlled mesh with an element size of $4.5 \cdot 10^{-7}$ – $1.01 \cdot 10^{-4}$ with a maximum element growth rate of 1.3, a curvature factor of 0.3 and a resolution for narrow regions of 1 was used for the calculation. As described in our previous work,⁵⁹ the EC effect was modeled with a time-dependent heat transfer study acting on the active (electroded) polymer layer and the subsequent heat dissipation to the surrounding non-active parts of a sample stack under the assumption of adiabatic boundary conditions. In order to reproduce the

experimental results and thus obtain the adiabatic ΔT_{EC} , the obtained numerical model was refined to fit the experimental data (Fig. S30, Supporting Information). Finally, a correction factor k , defined as the ratio between the adiabatic ΔT_{EC} obtained with the numerical model from inside the polymer film and the ΔT measured with the IR camera at the top of the black ink layer, was determined for different compositions over the whole temperature range. Further details of the method used can be found in our previous work^{47,59} and in Section S10 of the Supporting Information.

Indirect electrocaloric characterization

The indirect estimation of the EC effect was performed using the standard Landau phenomenological model.³⁹⁻⁴¹ This commonly used indirect approach allows prediction of ΔS_{EC} and ΔT_{EC} from the temperature dependence of low-field dielectric permittivity and high-field polarization data using the following simplified equation:

$$\Delta T_{EC} = -\frac{T}{c_p} \Delta S_{EC} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{T}{c_p} \beta (P_f^2 - P_i^2), \quad (1)$$

where c_p is the specific heat capacity, β is the Landau coefficient, P_f and P_i are the final (P_f in the case of EC cooling) and initial (P_{max} in the case of EC cooling) polarization, respectively. The polarization values were obtained directly from the P - E loops, while the parameter β was determined from the slope of the reciprocal dielectric permittivity above the Curie temperature (T_C) according to the following equation:

$$\frac{1}{\varepsilon_r \varepsilon_0} = \beta (T - T_C), \quad (2)$$

where ε_0 is the dielectric permittivity of vacuum. Further details on this method can be found in Refs. [39-41] and in Section S11 of the Supporting Information.

Author contributions

E.D. proposed the experimental study and F.D.D.S. provided the polymer powders. U.P. prepared the samples with valuable contributions from X.C. Y.N. performed the differential scanning calorimetry measurements. A.E.M. determined the sample thickness. U.P. performed low-field and high-field electrical characterization, infrared imaging and indirect electrocaloric characterization. V.K. performed finite element modeling. J.C. developed code for processing the electrical characterization and infrared camera data. T.G. made valuable contributions to the discussion and provided insightful comments. U.P. analyzed the data and wrote the manuscript with E.D. All authors contributed to the final version of the manuscript. E.D. and F.D.D.S. obtained funding and supervised the project.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

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